

Empowering LIS Graduates: Industrial Training as a quality assurance for the employability of Library and Information Science professionals in Nigeria

Mba, Chigozie Blessing¹, Iwuegbue Ishioma², and Regha Helen Okaku³

¹ Department of Library and Information Science, Dennis Osadebay University, Asaba Delta State, Nigeria | mba.blessing@dou.edu.ng & chigozieblessingmba@gmail.com
+2347032430486

² Department of Library and Information Science, Dennis Osadebay University, Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria | Ishioma.azonobi@dou.edu.ng | +2347066332589

³ Department of Library and Information Science, Dennis Osadebay University, Asaba , Delta State – Nigeria | regha.okaku@dou.edu.ng | +2348135868216

ABSTRACT

Background: This study examines the employability challenges faced by Library and Information Science (LIS) graduates in Nigeria, where employers frequently report deficits in practical skills among new graduates, impacting service delivery in libraries, information centers, and other organizations. The issue is attributed to inadequacies in the Industrial Training (IT) component of LIS education.

Method: A conceptual framework was adopted, drawing on existing literature on LIS education, industrial training schemes, and employability in Nigeria. The study reviewed these sources to identify factors affecting the quality of industrial training and propose solutions to enhance graduate employability.

Findings/Results: The review identified three critical factors undermining the quality of industrial training: a lack of synergy between LIS educators and industry practitioners, an outdated curriculum lacking emerging digital competencies, and insufficient duration and poor supervision of the industrial attachment program.

Implications: The findings suggest that addressing the identified deficiencies in industrial training is essential to bridge the theory-practice gap, thereby improving the practical skills and employability of LIS graduates and enhancing the professional standing of the LIS field in Nigeria.

Conclusion: The study concludes that the employability of LIS graduates in Nigeria is hindered by weaknesses in the industrial training component, and tackling these issues is vital for ensuring quality assurance in LIS education and improving service delivery.

Recommendations: The study recommends fostering formal collaborations between libraries, information centers, media centers, and library schools, conducting a comprehensive curriculum review to incorporate digital skills, and improving the duration and supervision of industrial attachment programs to align with the profession's needs and enhance graduate employability.

Keywords: Industrial Training, Employability, LIS Graduates, LIS Education, SIWES, Nigeria, Curriculum Development.

INTRODUCTION

The Library and Information Science (LIS) profession is multidisciplinary and practical in nature. The efficiency and effectiveness of service delivery in libraries, organizations, media and information centers is directly dependent on the practical competence of LIS graduates who

eventually become professionals within the field. However, in Nigeria, a growing disconnect exists between the theoretical knowledge imparted in LIS schools and the practical skills demanded by the labour market. Employers consistently note that many LIS graduates lack the hands-on proficiency required to perform core professional tasks, leading to inefficiency and poor productivity. This practical gap has serious implications as it results in low confidence among graduates and undergraduates in general, reduces their employment prospects, and eventually nurtures a negative perception of the LIS profession among prospective students and employers of labour. This undeniably calls for investigation and this paper attempts to address this problem through analysing the role and impact of Industrial Training component such as the Students' Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES), in the quality assurance designed to bridge this theory-practice gap in the production of quality LIS Graduates in Nigeria.

Industrial Training in the context of this paper may be defined as a process where students of LIS programmes are attached to functional libraries or other related organizations to gain experience, training and exposure appropriate in the labour market and the society at large. Ugwuanyi and Ezema (2010) described Industrial Training as a scheme jointly arranged between library schools and industries for all students studying technical courses requiring one form of industry exposure or another. The authors summarised the objectives of Industrial Training in Nigeria as follows: "To provide an avenue for students in institutions of higher learning to acquire industrial skills and experiences in their course of study".

Okpa, Mordi, and Udoh (2023) on their accord noted that Industrial Training inclusion in the LIS schools in Nigeria is a necessity. LIS students are placed in a company to complete supervised practical training (domestic or international), within a duration of time to be exposed with the practical knowledge of the profession before receiving a certificate, diploma, or bachelor's degree. It is one of the prerequisites for students majoring in library and information science who are enrolled in certificate, diploma, degree, and postgraduate programs. The objective of LIS education and training is the development and teaching of practical skills and knowledge in LIS for quality library service delivery in a work environment.

Bird, Chu, and Oguz (2015) affirmed that the training of students in industries is a key to imparting professional routine activities, and offers them the necessary understanding of institutional and industry-based challenges. This is very germane and important for the development of the LIS profession. A profession is an aspect of discipline, craft, or expertise whereby an individual or group of persons has moral and statutory rights conferred on them by a regulatory organisation or body of like minds, which empowers that individual to perform an activity or activities about the craft or discipline after meeting satisfactory training requirements, of the parent organisation.

Olubiyo (2022) defines a profession as a specialised calling, vocation, or occupation made up of comprehensive education and training in a specific field with an intention to apply and serve humanity. The LIS as a profession began with a study or an academic programme from the undergraduate level, which requires a 4-year study whereby the student graduates after satisfying theory and practical requirements based on satisfactory performance, which earns them the Bachelor of Library Science (BLS) or Bachelor of Library and Information Science (BLIS) degree. The award of this degree makes it professional in both practice and theory of this noble discipline.

The professional expectation of LIS graduates places huge responsibilities on the teaching and teachers of the LIS academic programme especially with the evolving trends in service delivery as well as in knowledge organization which has to conform to the technological trends of the profession. Diso and Njoku (2007) observe that the library of the 21st century has been appropriately termed a digital library. However, the library in 21st-century Nigeria will have to combine digital and traditional library elements of electronic literacy. The authors also pointed out that training information professionals of 21st-century in Nigeria is a task LIS educators must be prepared for it. Therefore, for the LIS educators to achieve their desired proficiency in their products, they need to synergise in the activities of knowledge impartation, as this practice would also help graduates to respond and rise to global challenges and demands of the 21st century employers of labour. Tamaro and Virkus (2005) posit that the professionalism of the LIS programme should be motivated by the desire to respond to global challenges and trends in strengthening the models of educating students through an institutional tutor exchange programme. Nigerian LIS educators can initiate, embrace, and foster teamwork in the teaching of the LIS programme.

Aside from the expert and strategic knowledge imparted to students, the LIS curriculum is also supposed to empower teachers and the teaching of the LIS programme and other inherent programmes in making their graduates and products what they ought to be. The practical nature of libraries ordinarily places emphasis on all who are associated with the curriculum design (NUC), teaching, and learning of LIS. Mbagwu, Okoye, and Anyanwu (2018) opine that the library is a barn of Information and knowledge, and hence information managers and professionals are meant to be equipped properly to impart knowledge to students for the possible challenges of the "time". They assert that proper education and training are given to the students of Library and Information Science in order to contribute effectively in workplaces without fear. The LIS education, an important segment of the profession, is fundamentally and inevitably affected by globalisation.

The challenges of globalisation demand that LIS schools worldwide review and change the contents of their curricula to equip their graduates with the knowledge and skills that would enable them succeed in the ever-changing LIS marketplace. Thus, available literature indicates that LIS education has been primarily and frequently changing in many countries (Abubakar, 2021). Similarly, the LIS education globally has undergone all-round evolution processes, and just like time, it revolves and evolves with trends of seasons in both theory and practice. This trend of evolution is a challenge to most LIS educators to brace up with the evolving trends, especially in the education of LIS students in order to prepare and acquaint them with the basic skills of service and information provision in a dynamic society.

Mohammed as cited in Olubiyo (2022) asserted that the need for the provision of library and information science education and the acquisition of relevant knowledge, techniques and skills for effective and efficient library and information work is needed now more than before due to differences in library and information systems, services and infrastructure to cope with the changing needs and expectations of the 21st century people, societies, communities and institutions. Library routine activities, beginning from the library space itself, such as cataloguing and classification, readers' services, loans and discharging of books, acquisition and collection development, and weeding have changed dramatically with a more approach. Aslam (2022) argues

that keeping pace with evolving trends in innovation of systems and approaches in the swift dynamism of librarianship has been challenging for most library educators.

This study adopts a conceptual review approach. This methodology involves identifying and synthesizing relevant literature to develop a new conceptual framework or perspective on a problem. Data for this paper was gathered through a comprehensive review of existing scholarly articles, books, and official documents from bodies like the Industrial Training Fund (ITF) concerning LIS education, industrial training, and employability in Nigeria. The literature was analyzed thematically to identify recurring challenges, proposed solutions, and gaps in the current system, leading to the recommendations presented herein.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study of LIS requires effective teaching and exposure to hands-on practical exercises from industries. Despite the mandate of industrial training, there is insufficient evidence that LIS graduates from Nigerian universities possess the practical competencies required by the modern information sector and industrial demands. This deficiency is evident during job interviews and in the workplace, where graduates struggle with routines like cataloguing, classification, and digital resource management. The problem appears within the execution of the industrial training program itself, including inadequate supervision, an obsolete curriculum, and an insufficient training duration. Hence, requires investigation to understand the major factor contributing to this insufficiency and the impact Industrial Training had made in the production of quality LIS graduates in Nigeria.

OBJECTIVE

This paper aims to critically examine the role and impact of industrial training as a quality assurance mechanism for the employability of LIS graduates in Nigeria. It analyzed the existing challenges and proposes evidence-based strategies for enhancing the industrial training program to better prepare students for the workforce in the future.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Concept of Industrial Training

The concept and actualisation of Industrial training in Nigeria kicked off in 1973 in reaction to the unemployability of Nigerian graduates and their labour market unfitness due to poor industry knowledge (ITF,1973). Similarly, Simisaye et al. (2018) define SIWES as a phase of librarianship education in which undergraduates at library schools are given a chance to get practical experience in a library setting, which is a vital component of the library school programme. Therefore, the industrial training program is a general program designed for all Nigerian students enrolled in the polytechnics and universities whose disciplines are practical-based to attach to industries as well as fields in order to match theory to practice in order to achieve a balance between experience, knowledge, and understanding of the discipline.

The ITF document (2022) explains that the 'Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) is a Skills Training Program designed to prepare and expose Students of Universities, Polytechnics, Colleges of Technology, Colleges of Agriculture, and Colleges of Education for the Industrial Work situation they are likely to meet after graduation. The Scheme affords Students the opportunity of familiarizing and exposing themselves to handling equipment and machinery that are usually not available in their institutions. Some of the objectives of this scheme according to ITF (2022) are:

- a) Provide an avenue for Students in Institutions of Higher Learning to acquire industrial skills and experience in their course of study.
- b) Prepare Students for the industrial work situation they are to meet after graduation.
- c) Expose Students to work methods and techniques in handling equipment and machinery that may not be available in their Institutions.
- d) Make the transition from school to the world of work easier, and enhance Students' contacts for later job placement.
- e) Provide Students with an opportunity to apply their knowledge in a real-world situation, thereby bridging the gap between theory and practice.
- f) Enlist and strengthen Employers' involvement in the entire education process and prepare Students for employment after graduation.

Industrial Training for LIS Students and Profession

Empirical research has revealed that graduates lacking fundamental knowledge in courses offered in universities could not fulfill the demands and expectations of the profession in LIS practice (Abraham-Ibe cited in Madu et al. 2023), as well as in the labour markets. Madu et al., (2023) found that industrial training has positive influence on the academic performance of the students though besieged with challenges that could hamper on their employability. This may be due to the high performance required for employment in a variety of settings and organizations.

Josiah, Mordi, and Udoh (2023) found that training students using industry practice and procedures improves knowledge, literacy, academic, practical developments, and general professional competency. The study further revealed that the extent of academic achievement of LIS students as regards industrial training was demonstrated in the study as skills demonstrations, excellent performance, enlightenment, experience, and learning new things in the profession. Ode (2017) observed that SIWES programme helps the students to develop basic professional skills and it is beneficial to their overall educational development and employability. According to Ojokuku et al.,(2015) SIWES aims to bridge the current gap between theory and practice and expose students to the required skills for a smooth transition from the classroom to the world of work. Griffin and Celhoso cited in Madu et al (2023) noted that SIWES allows students to connect with others to evaluate their talents and performance. It helps to enhance cooperation, problem-solving, and other essential employability skills. Such experience (SIWES) leads to increased career opportunities for graduates (Madu et.al, 2023). Likewise, there are approaches to assuring quality in the training of LIS students; these approaches are essential in achieving productive quality in students, educators, and graduates.

Synergy amongst Educators

Synergy is crucial in the survival and health of any model. Collaboration and partnership in the education of students would yield greater results. Abubakar (2021) noted that the LIS education has been experiencing a radical change, especially in the last couple of decades, which results in fundamental changes in all its structures. With synergy in the education of students, academic professionals can go on exchange in different library schools to teach and impart knowledge and methodology. According to Roy and Habib (2024), effective collaboration between library and information science academics and practitioners is vital for the professional growth and success of individuals working in the field. This suggests that the absence of such formal collaboration in Nigeria is a critical missing link in preparing students for the realities of the modern information workplace. It facilitates the exchange of knowledge, skills, and innovative practices, which, in turn, enhance the quality of library services. It allows for the integration of theoretical knowledge with practical experience, resulting in more effective and efficient library operations. However, the lack of studies on fostering collaboration between library and information science academics and practitioners in Bangladesh presents a notable research gap.

Although this could pose financial constraints on the institution, the benefits to both students and the institution would be unparalleled. The benefits of synergy in the education of LIS students would help improve professional confidence amongst students, strengthen cross-institutional connections and alignments, promote the LIS profession, and sustain passion and interest in LIS programs. Similarly, synergy in the education of LIS students would help educators better themselves in knowledge impartation. Strengthen his professional connections, expose him to their professional models and conduct, and improve professional ties in the LIS educators' family. When synergy is in practice in Library schools, students could perform better, gain universal knowledge empowerment, and help in sustaining the longevity of the profession in standards nationwide. Research such as Sacchanand (2012) considers collaboration to be essential for changes in the higher education environment, a paradigm shift in LIS, and the changing role of teaching faculty and librarians. Similarly, Lillard and Wales (2003) noted that academic librarians and LIS educators work together to seek creative approaches to strengthening LIS education.

Curriculum Quality

Curriculum is the bedrock of any education all over the world, without which no educational institution, regardless of the level, would be able to make a meaningful impact. Curriculum is a compass that directs the pace and extent of teaching as well as determines the extent to which students learn. It plays the role of a medication prescription in the curative process of an ailment; it is a major determinant of whether the ailment should be permanently cured based on the prescribed application or not.

A curriculum is a stipulated list of templates for subjects, topics, and schemes that are meant to serve as a professional guide to the education, teaching, and training of students. The curriculum largely determines the extent to which students are taught and how much they should know. A weak curriculum would produce weak LIS graduates. The LIS curriculum is meant to be periodically reviewed to accommodate emerging trends, especially as librarianship is about information service delivery as well as a hands-on practical discipline. The quality of the LIS curriculum should be reviewed by professionals before its functional application to LIS students.

Technological advancements and social dynamics in the field have brought about significant and tremendous changes to the Library and Information Science (LIS) education globally.

LIS programs are skill-oriented, and to acquire adequate skill, training must occur in the appropriate environment. The availability and functionalities of technological equipment aid a faster learning procedure and help to produce efficiency in knowledge. Researchers such as Ojukwu, Emeahara, Aboyade, and Chris-Israel (2015) have found that facilities such as internet connectivity, desktop computers, and electronic resources, etc., in libraries improved students' professional knowledge and enhanced their capacity and ranked 93.7% in accounting for their perception about professional education of the LIS program.

In a similar development, the industry training of LIS students does not only depend on educators and field supervisors, the material and financial support from the management of academic institutions where students learn could be greatly impactful in motivating and charging students to commitment and passion for industry and that is why Afolabi and Tagwal (2022) corroborated this in their research findings on the influence of industrial training of LIS students in Osun state. Nevertheless, Yusuf (2014) differed in his opinion and findings about the industrial training of LISS. He opined that the training of LISS during theoretical classroom courses should be done simultaneously with practical demonstration, as the lectures teach. He suggested that industry educators should also be part of the classroom theoretical teaching approach to be able to demonstrate activities and tools required for adequate education and professional knowledge.

Abubakar (2021) affirms that the LIS profession is not left out; the LIS education has been experiencing a radical change, especially in the last couple of decades, which results in fundamental changes in all its structures. Such changes are pervasive, global, and profound. Furthermore, the LIS profession has become interdisciplinary, with more studies integrating into it. Studies such as Digitization, Metadata management, Data Science, Information studies, Knowledge management, Information Architecture, Content Management, Computer science, etc. have become revolutionary for the profession, and as such, the LIS curriculum to prove its merit and assure the quality of its education must incorporate these emerging trends in the curriculum. This fundamental revolution has implications for the profession and has led to the offering of diverse/joint degrees by LIS schools, especially in the advanced countries, employment of new faculty, new curricular offerings, mode of delivery as well as changes in the market place for LIS graduates who now require new skills and competencies (Abubakar, 2021). According to Assefa and Wang (2018), the LIS field is increasingly becoming interdisciplinary and diverse, with many new areas being offered.

Considering the recent transformations that have resulted in globalization, which is accompanied by massive radical changes in all spheres of human endeavour, LIS educational programmes in Nigeria are expected to be amenable to such radical changes. Therefore, changes in curriculum, teaching and learning methods as well as assessment systems are necessary. Moreover, it is critical to note that advancements in technologies (ICTs) have been the driving force for all these developments. Digital technologies have transformed LIS education and libraries in general, and the reality for the LIS field requires that LIS education must be technologically-based and market-driven at the same time. Tella, et al., (2018) in their survey noted that the LIS curriculum has to adjust LIS courses to include new areas such as ICT skills (Internet searching skills, database

management, website design and management, and networking). Others are publishing, multi-media applications, electronic resources management and information literacy etc. researchers such as, Nonthacumjane (2011) outlined possible nomenclature of courses to be reflected in a revised LIS curriculum: personal skills (analytical, creative and flexibility), generic skills (communication, critical thinking, and information literacy) and discipline-specific (metadata, digital archiving, content management and database management).

Nevertheless, there are skills and competencies LIS educators, students, and graduates are meant to acquire, and these skills would only be accessed through the transformation of the LIS curriculum. Researchers like Narasappa and Kumar (2016) observed that the wake of digital technology as categorized skills necessary for inclusion into the curriculum into four: professional competencies, personal competencies, soft skills, ICT skills, and networking. Similarly, LIS educators are professionals and are meant to apply models that enrich knowledge and practice while in their educational roles. When an educator is an expert and vast in topics, quality would be brought into the teaching models and knowledge impartation. Okonoko et al., (2023) revealed that critical thinking, creativity and imagination, communication and information management and willingness to learn as employability skills are required from LIS graduates as it is likely to increase their likelihood of finding employment and succeeding in their chosen profession.

Extended duration of industry training

Industrial is the training ground and threshold on which the LIS profession is anchored. This is because the LIS profession is practical-based and industry compliant, and therefore the industrial training is a skilled program which is a part of the LIS program where undergraduate students are exposed to industry practices and schedules. In order to produce employment-ready graduates and job market compliant, it is imperative that undergraduate training incorporates both theory and practice for a more balanced outcome. Researchers such as Anho (2011) and Edukugho (2012) corroborate the belief that the training obtained from most tertiary institutions is mostly theoretical, and so does not equip graduates with the necessary competencies and skills demanded by the job market. Consequently, over the years, there have been calls for a bridging of the gap between theory and practice, and in response, the student industrial exercise was established to equip potential graduates with the practical skills in their disciplines, and the LIS profession is not left out (Akerejola, 2004; Ugwuanyi & Ezema, 2010).

The scheme is jointly arranged between the schools and industries for all students studying technical courses requiring one form of industry exposure or another. According to Ugwuanyi and Ezema (2010) the specific objectives of the scheme are to provide an avenue for students in institutions of higher learning to acquire industrial skills and experiences in their course of study. It is a stepping tool to having a work experience and it also creates a pathway of long lasting work experience which is capable in taking one far in life (Ugwoke, et al., 2023). However, in librarianship, most of the practical exercises involve the routine activities of information provision and processing, such as the organisation of knowledge like cataloguing and classification, shelving and shelf reading, weeding and selection criteria, collection development and acquisition, archives and records management, data and preservation techniques, digital and technological inclusion, etc. Without the industry and knowledgeable industry supervisors, LIS students would not be able to perform at their best as graduates.

Josiah, Ngozi and Udoh (2023) affirms that the industrial training provides an avenue for students in the Nigerian universities to acquire industrial skills and experience during their course of study; it prepares students for the work situation they are likely to encounter after graduation; it exposed the students to work methods and techniques in handling equipment and machinery required for the efficient practice of the profession with an opportunity to apply their theoretical knowledge in real work situation thereby bridging the gap between theory and practice. Obim and Wagwu (2023) in a study noted that students' opportunities for industrial training have a huge impact on their employability. Already in the LIS curriculum, practical industry training has been provided, as well as the duration for the hands-on learning exercise; however, evidence from some LIS graduates has not shown that the duration of the industry training is sufficient to master all that is to be learnt. According to the LIS curriculum, industrial training duration for undergraduates is a minimum of 120 days (6months), from which observation shows that it will not sufficient, as this duration does not exclusively apply to all institutions.

CONCLUSION

The empowerment of LIS graduates is fundamentally tied to the quality of their practical training. The current industrial training model in Nigeria, while well-intentioned, requires significant reform to function as an effective quality assurance mechanism. This review concludes that poor collaboration, an outdated curriculum, and an insufficient training duration are some of the impediments to LIS education in Nigeria but enhancing proficiency in practice (hands-on Practical) not only theory can help improve employability and elevate the status of the profession at large.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this review, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Library schools should establish formal partnerships with leading libraries and information centers. This should include involving practitioners in curriculum review panels and facilitating exchange programs for educators.
2. There should be an urgent review of the LIS curriculum is needed to fully integrate ICT skills, digital resource management, data curation, and other emerging competencies demanded by the job market.
3. Heads of libraries and industry supervisors should be trained on their role in providing a comprehensive and immersive learning experience for attached students.

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